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Research Article

RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Metformin and Telmisartan in Tablet Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

A robust and efficient Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Telmisartan in tablet dosage form. The method employed a C18 column Xterra (150 x 4.6 mm, 5mm) with a mobile phase consisting of phosphate buffer (pH 4.0) and acetonitrile in a 60:40 v/v ratio. The flow rate was set at 1.0 mL/min, and detection was performed at 210 nm. The method demonstrated excellent resolution and reproducibility, with retention times of Metformin and Telmisartan being 2.70 and 3.64 minutes, respectively. Validation studies confirmed the specificity, linearity, accuracy, and precision of the method, with a linear range of 62.5-375ppm & 5-30 ppm for both drugs. The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were determined to be 0.02 mcg/ml and 0.07 mcg/ml for Metformin, and 0.02mcg/ml and 0.06 mcg/ml for Telmisartan, respectively. Recovery studies indicated high accuracy, with recoveries ranging from 99% to 100%. The method was also found to be robust under varied conditions. This validated RP-HPLC method is suitable for routine quality control analysis of Metformin and Telmisartan in pharmaceutical formulations, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards.

INTRODUCTION

Metformin:

Metformin is an oral antidiabetic drug in the biguanide class, first-line drug of choice for the treatment of type 2 diabetes, in peculiar, in over weight and obese people and those with normal kidney function. Metformin's use in gestational diabetes has been limited by safety

matters. It is also used in the treatment of polycystic ovary syndrome, has been investigated for other diseases where insulin resistance may be an important factor, it works by suppressing glucose production by the liver.

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Fig 1: Structure of Metformin

IUPAC Name: 1-Carbamimidamido-N,N-Dimethyl methanimidamide

Molecular formula: C₄H₁₁N₅

Molecular weight: 129.1636 g/mol

Half-life: 6.2 hours. Duration of action is 8-12 hours.

Category: Antidiuretic Agents

TELMISARTAN:

Telmisartan is an angiotensin II receptor antagonist (ARB) used in the management of hypertension. Generally, angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs) such as telmisartan bind to the angiotensin II type 1 (AT1) receptors with high affinity, causing inhibition of the action of angiotensin II on vascular smooth muscle, ultimately leading to a reduction in arterial blood pressure. Recent studies suggest that telmisartan may also have PPAR-gamma agonistic properties that could potentially confer beneficial metabolic effects.

Fig 2 Structure of Telmisartan

IUPAC Name: 2-(4-{[4-methyl-6-(1-methyl-1H-1,3-benzodiazol-2-yl)-2-propyl-1H-1,3-benzodiazol-1-yl]methyl}phenyl)benzoic acid

Molecular formula: C₃₃H₃₀N₄O

Molecular weight: 514.64 gm/mol

Half-life: Bi-exponential decay kinetics with a terminal elimination half-life of approximately 24 hours.

Category: Antihypertensive

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

Metformin and Telmesartan, Combination Metformin and Telmesartan tablets, distilled water, acetonitrile, phosphate buffer, ammonium acetate buffer, glacialacetic acid, methanol, potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer, tetra hydrofuran, tri ethyl amine, ortho-phosphoric acid etc.

Instrument:

1. HPLC instrument used was of WATERS HPLC 2965 SYSTEM with Auto Injector and PDA Detector. Software used is Empower
2. UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2mm and 10mm and matched quartz was be used for measuring absorbance for Metformin and Telmesartan solutions.

Methods:

Preparation of buffer:

Buffer: 1 ml OPA in a 1000ml of Volumetric flask add about 900ml of milli-Q water added and degas to sonicate and finally make up the volume with water then PH adjusted to 3.6 with dil. Orthophosphoric acid solution.

Standard Preparation: (250µg/ml Metformin and 20µg/ml Telmisartan)

Accurately Weighed and transferred 25mg & 5mg of Metformin and Telmisartan working Standards into 10 ml and 25ml clean dry volumetric flasks separately, add 3/4th ml of diluent, sonicated for 30 minutes and make up to the final volume with diluents. From the above each stock solutions, 1 ml was pipeted out in to a 10ml Volumetric flask and then make up to the final volume with diluent.

Sample preparation: 5 tablets were weighed and calculate the average weight of each tablet then the weight equivalent to 5 tablets was transferred into

a 100ml volumetric flask, 70ml of diluent added and sonicated for 30 min, further the volume made up with diluent and filtered. From the filtered solution 0.1ml was pipeted out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made upto 10ml with diluent.

Method Development:

Trial 1

Column Used : Kromosil 150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .
Mobile phase : Buffer methanol (50:50)
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Wavelength : 210nm
Temperature : 30°C
Injection Volume : 10 μ l

Fig: 3 Trial chromatogram 1

Trial 2

Column Used : Xterra 150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .
Mobile phase : Buffer: Acetonitrile methanol (50:40:10)
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Wavelength : 210nm
Temperature : 30°C
Injection Volume : 10 μ l

Fig: 2 Trial chromatogram 2

Trial 3:

Column Used : Xterra 150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .
Buffer used : 0.1% OPA
Mobile phase : Buffer: acetonitrile (55:45A)
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Wavelength : 210nm
Temperature : 30°C
Injection Volume : 10 μ l

Fig: 3 Trial chromatogram 3

Optimized Method: Drugs were eluted with good retention time, resolution; all the system suitable parameters like Plate count and Tailing factor were within the limits.

Column Used : Xterra150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .
Buffer used : 0.1% OPA
Mobile phase : Buffer: Acetonitrile (60:40A)
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Diluent : Water: methanol 50:50
Wavelength : 210nm
Temperature : 30°C
Injection Volume : 10 μ l

Fig: 4. Optimized Chromatogram

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

System suitability: All the system suitability parameters are within range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

Table: 1 System suitability studies of Metformin and Telmesartan

Property	Metformin	Telmesartan
Retention time (tR)	2.701± 0.3 min	3.640±0.3min
Theoretical plates(N)	2713± 163.48	3705± 163.48
Tailing factor (T)	1.35± 0.117	1.20± 0.117

Fig: 5 Typical chromatogram of Metformin and Telmesartan

Linearity: Six Linear concentrations 50ppm - 300ppm of Metformin and 5ppm - 30ppm of Telmesartan are prepared and Injected. Regression equation of the Metformin and Telmesartan are found to be $y = 16786x + 673.7$ and $y = 40365x + 1626$ and regression co-efficient was 0.999.

Table:2 Calibration data of Metformin and Telmesartan

S. No	Metformin Concentration Metformin (µg/ml) Response (mV)		Telmesartan Concentration Telmesartan Response	
	CONC	RESPONSE	CONC	RESPONSE
1	0	0	0	0
2	62.5	997842	5	202266
3	125	2102553	10	393075
4	187.5	3247781	15	626474
5	250	4151914	20	812422
6	312.5	5286514	25	1010212
7	375	6249487	30	1205306

Fig: 6 Calibration curve of Metformin

Fig:6 Calibration curve of Telmesartan

Precision:

Intraday precision (Repeatability): Intraday precision was performed and % RSD for

Metformin and Telmesartan were found to be 0.43% and 1.04% respectively.

Table: 3 Repeatability data for Metformin and Telmesartan

S. No.	Metformin	Telmesartan
1	4194425	809790
2	4198279	817824
3	4177547	810827
4	4165200	828601
5	4150690	829452
6	4172834	822917
Mean	4176496	819902
Std. Dev.	17911.0	8542.7
%RSD	0.43	1.04

Fig. 7 Repeatability Chromatogram of Metformin and Telmesartan

Accuracy: Three concentrations 50%, 100%, amount Recovered and % Recovery were 150%, were injected in a triplicate manner and displayed in

Table 4. Accuracy data of Metformin and Telmesartan

Sample	Concentration (%) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Recovery (%)	%RSD
Metformin	125	125.59	100.48	0.22
	250	252.59	101.04	0.59
	375	377.87	100.76	0.25
Telmesartan	10	10.12	101.24	0.72
	20	20.05	100.26	0.79
	30	30.21	100.70	0.10

Robustness: Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate, mobile phase ratio, and temperature are made but there were no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH Guide lines.

Table 5. Robustness data of Metformin and Telmesartan

S.NO	Robustness condition	Metformin %RSD	Telmesartan %RSD
1	Flow minus	0.2	0.35
2	Flow Plus	0.6	0.8
3	Mobile phase minus	0.0	0.33
4	Mobile phase Plus	0.2	0.3
5	Temperature minus	0.9	0.2
6	Temperature Plus	0.4	1.7

Assay: Standard preparations are made from the API and Sample Preparations are from Formulation. Both sample and standards are injected six homogeneous samples. Drug in the formulation was estimated by taking the standard as the reference. The Average %Assay was calculated and found to be 99.79 and 100.51 for Metformin and Telmesartan respectively.

Table :6 Assay of Tablet

S. No.	Metformin %Assay	Telmesartan %Assay
1	100.22	99.27
2	100.31	100.25
3	99.82	99.40
4	99.52	101.58
5	99.17	101.68
6	99.70	100.88
AVG	99.79	100.51
STDEV	0.428	1.05
%RSD	0.43	1.04

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS:**Table: 7. Summary Table**

Parameters	Metformin	Telmesartan
Calibration range(mcg/ml)	62.5-375ppm	5-30ppm
Optimized wavelength	210nm	210nm
Mobilephase (Acetonitrile: Buffer)	60:40	60:40
Column	Xterra 150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .	Xterra 150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .
Retention time	2.701min	3.640min
Regression equation(Y*)	$y = 16786x + 673.7$	$y = 40365x + 1626$
Precision (%RSD*)	0.43	1.04
% Recovery	99.79	100.51
LOD(mcg/ml)	0.02	0.02
LOQ(mcg/ml)	0.07	0.06

CONCLUSIONS

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Metformin and Telmesartan in tablet form. The retention times (Rt's) of Metformin and Telmesartan were found to be 2.701min and 3.640min. Percentage RSD of the Metformin was found to be 0.43 and for Telmesartan was 1.04 and the %Recoveries were gained as 99.79% for Metformin and 100.51% for Telmesartan.

LOD, LOQ values are from regression equations of Metformin and Telmesartan were 0.02, 0.07ppm and 0.02, 0.06ppm resp.

Regression equation of Metformin is $y = 16786x + 673.7$, Telmesartan is $y = 40365x + 1626$. In this proposed method retention times (Rt's) were decreased so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

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